

Effects of teaching strategies on scientific inquiry in students of a public educational institution

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Abstract—The present study presented the objective of determining the effects of applying didactic strategies in the achievement of the scientific inquiry competence in the area of Science and Technology, in students of the VI cycle of secondary education of a public educational institution, Paracas-2024. In this sense, it was based on SDG No. 4 Quality Education. In the methodology, the applied type was considered, with a quantitative approach, with a quasi-experimental design, with a population of 100 students and a sample of 64 students from 1 "A" and 1 "B" of a public institution in Paracas. The technique was observation and the instrument used was a questionnaire or test based on the rubric and the validity was content and reliability presented a value of 0.953, interpreted as high reliability. It concluded that the application of didactic strategies has significant effects on the achievement of the scientific inquiry competence in the area of Science and Technology in students of the VI cycle of secondary education of a public educational institution, Paracas-2024; Supported by a $p = 0.000$ and $z = -6.788$, which suggested that the implemented strategies developed scientific inquiry processes.

Keywords - Scientific inquiry, teaching strategies, design, data analysis,

I. INTRODUCTION

It was also considered that this research was important because, in a globalized world where scientific and technological advances evolve rapidly, the ability to investigate, question, and generate new knowledge has become a key driving force for meeting the challenges of the twenty-first century. These conditions have transformed the classroom into a dynamic environment for discovery and active learning. In this context, a strong education in scientific inquiry, supported by effective strategies, enables students not only to assimilate ideas but also to develop the skills necessary to conduct research, think critically, and independently find solutions to various challenges. Goal number 4 of the 2030 Agenda supports this proposal by promoting quality and equitable education that fosters learning opportunities at all levels of the educational system, ensuring equal opportunities for everyone (United Nations [UN], 2024).

According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO] (2020), science and technology play a crucial role in addressing the goals proposed in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), promoting an education aimed at preparing students to solve complex problems. However, at the global level, many educational programs have faced challenges in effectively integrating these disciplines into the curriculum, which has limited the development of skills and competencies related to critical thinking and problem-solving (OECD, 2022).

In many Latin American nations, the scarcity or complete absence of ongoing teacher training, along with restricted access to high-quality educational resources, has had a detrimental impact on teaching practices. This situation has resulted in inconsistencies in instructional strategies that could otherwise improve student learning, particularly among those disadvantaged by inadequate education from insufficiently trained teachers, often called “strong teachers.”

Across Spanish-speaking countries, various efforts have been undertaken to overcome the challenges observed in classrooms; however, these initiatives have often been limited by the insufficient application of such approaches in everyday teaching, preventing their full and effective implementation.

Thus, enhancing the Indaga competence is essential for strengthening students' scientific abilities and ensuring their readiness for a constantly evolving world. It is crucial to emphasize that teacher preparation in the teaching of Science and Technology (S&T), along with ongoing professional development, plays a vital role. This is because the area is grounded in an inquiry-based approach, as well as in scientific and technological literacy—key elements in student formation that promote the successful achievement of competencies related to observing the physical world, engaging in scientific inquiry, and developing reflective and creative analytical skills, all of which foster a deeper understanding of scientific principles (Ministry of Education [Minedu], 2020).

Based on the aforementioned points, the interest arose to conduct a study on the effects of using didactic techniques (DT) in the area of Science and Technology (S&T), specifically focused on the first competence—scientific inquiry—which aim to improve the process of knowledge transmission and acquisition among students. In this regard, the following general research question was formulated: What are the effects of applying didactic strategies on the scientific inquiry competence in the area of Science and Technology among sixth-cycle secondary school students at a public educational institution in Paracas, 2024?

In international background studies Apdoludin et al. (2024) conducted a study aimed at comparing critical thinking skills in relation to academic performance. The methodology involved two groups of 26 students each. The study concluded that there was a significant improvement in learning outcomes associated with the proposed program, with results showing ($9.01 > 2.069$). The authors emphasized the importance of ensuring that students critically reflect on various materials, as this approach enhances their mastery of knowledge and leads to improved learning outcomes in the sciences.

Mendoza-Mendoza and Loor-Colamarco (2022) conducted a study aimed at developing a methodology based on didactic strategies applied in the field of science to enhance students' scientific thinking. The study concluded that the teaching of natural sciences has a significant influence on the development of scientific thinking among learners. However, it was observed that these strategies were often implemented separately and without an integrated plan, which limited their effectiveness in the learning process. This finding is particularly relevant to the present research, as it highlights that the mere application of didactic strategies does not guarantee the effective development of scientific competencies unless they are coherently and systematically integrated.

Castro & Vega (2021) conducted an analysis with the main objective of examining the influence of motivational and metacognitive strategies on the learning process of physics. Using a positivist-interpretive approach, data were collected from a representative sample of 35 students. The results showed that 66% of the students did not consider learning physics difficult; however, 51% felt that instruction was excessively focused on theory. Furthermore, all participants reported the absence of a science laboratory, while 68% indicated that teachers consistently encouraged their motivation to learn physics. These findings suggest that, despite teachers' efforts to inspire students, the educational approach remains predominantly theoretical, hindering practical learning. In conclusion, the study highlights the importance of incorporating pedagogical techniques such as the metacognitive strategy "Heuristic V" to foster motivation, stimulate students' interest in science, and enhance their learning experience.

Quesada-Soto et al. (2024) designed an educational platform aimed at promoting pedagogical strategies for teaching chemistry in secondary education, with the goal of offering an alternative approach to traditional instruction. A diagnostic evaluation was conducted, and two groups were established: an experimental group and a control group. During the process, four key topics were addressed. Teachers gave positive feedback on the platform, emphasizing its format, content, and design. The results showed that 20% (9 students) of the control group achieved an advanced performance level, whereas 44% of the experimental group who used the platform reached the advanced level. These findings indicate that students who used the platform

demonstrated superior academic performance, suggesting that its implementation facilitated a more meaningful improvement in learning the evaluated content.

Sopla et al. (2024) conducted an analysis aimed at assessing the progress made in experimental skills as part of scientific inquiry (SI) among students in the Science and Technology course through the implementation of didactic strategies. A pretest and posttest were applied, and the study concluded that the application of the scientific method is essential, as it generates a positive impact not only on students' acquisition of knowledge but also on their professional development.

It presented a methodological justification aligned with the research objectives and questions, which made it possible to obtain valid, reliable, and relevant data to assess the outcomes of implementing teaching procedures related to the development of the scientific inquiry (SI) competence among students. According to Hernández-Sampieri and Mendoza (2018), the methodological justification involved selecting data collection techniques and designs that ensured the rigor and robustness of the conclusions reached.

Regarding the theories related to the variable didactic strategies, these have been discussed and developed throughout the history of education and are grounded in constructivism. Novak (1977) proposed that this approach views knowledge as a socially constructed process in which students are the creators of their own learning, building upon their prior knowledge. Furthermore, Bruner (1960) stated that the constructivist learning model is based on discovery. These theories emphasize that students acquire knowledge actively through exploration and the process of discovering their own understanding.

Similarly, other strategies are proposed, such as *collaborative learning*, which aims to harness students' social and emotional resources to develop teamwork, leadership, and conflict-resolution skills. Therefore, when this strategy is implemented in the classroom, it is essential to organize students into groups, allowing them to reflect and understand through collaborative abilities and scientific communication skills (Johnson & Johnson, 1999).

Teaching strategies represent the art and techniques of effective teaching, emphasizing the relevance of methodologies that facilitate learning (Herrera et al., 2023). Along the same lines, Colorado & Gutiérrez (2016) stated that teaching strategies are planned tasks designed to achieve effective teaching and learning processes. These strategies enable teachers to develop activities aimed at fostering science learning.

The Problem-Based Learning strategy enables students to solve problems involving scientific content. Through this approach, learners work collaboratively on activities—such as science experiments conducted in laboratories—that allow them to explore, experiment, and obtain meaningful results (Eggen & Kauchak, 2015).

In Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL), students engage in active investigation while simultaneously experimenting, formulating hypotheses, making predictions, and testing them in laboratory settings (Servicio de Innovación Educativa, 2020). Employing diverse strategies allows for the implementation of tasks that effectively contribute to the achievement of competencies (Kurt & Sezek, 2021).

In competency-based learning, the focus is on strengthening critical thinking, reflection, and clear, effective communication skills, while utilizing various resources for problem-solving (Martínez et al., 2012). Learning activities are structured sequentially and designed to be relevant for achieving specific competencies (Hartikainen et al., 2019).

The theoretical approach to research competencies is supported by scientific inquiry, which enables individuals to study and develop from a personal to a professional level (Chen & Xu, 2017). In this regard,

the development of research competencies should be ensured through proper training and the implementation of strategies that serve as effective alternatives for students (García & Aznar, 2019).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Design

The design of the study followed a quasi-experimental design, as it compared an experimental group with a control group composed of students who did not receive the intervention, allowing the researchers to infer the effects of implementing the intervention program. This type of design was employed when researchers were unable to randomly control or manipulate the assignment of participants, which commonly occurs in natural settings or when pre-existing groups are already established (Hernández-Sampieri & Mendoza, 2018).

2.2. Participants

The population was a sample of 64 students from grades 1 “A” and 1 “B” of a public institution. The first-grade section “A” was designated as the control group, while section “B” served as the experimental group. A non-probabilistic convenience sampling method was used, meaning the selection of participants was not based on probability but rather on the specific objectives of the study (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018).

2.3. Measuring instruments

For this research the instrument used in the study was a questionnaire or test based on a rubric adapted. According to Hernández and Mendoza (2018), questionnaires in research are an essential tool for collecting information in a structured manner.

2.4. Procedure

The procedure was carried out: first, a pretest was administered to measure the dependent variable. Second, an intervention program titled “Scientific Inquiry” was implemented. Third, a post-test was applied to obtain the results of the research study.

III. RESULTS

TABLE I
RESULTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENTIFIC INQUIRY

Level	Control group				Experimental group			
	Pretest		posttest		Pretest		Posttest	
	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%
Beginner	31	100	29	93.5	31	100	0	0
Process	0	0	2	3.2	0	0	0	0
Expected								
Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	9.7
Outstanding								
Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	28	90.3
Total								

Fig. 1 Results of the development of the scientific inquiry

The results shown in Table 1 and Figure 1 indicate that, in the pretest, both the control and experimental groups obtained similar results, remaining at the initial level. However, in the post-test, the experimental group showed 9.7% at the expected achievement level and 90.3% at the outstanding level, demonstrating that the program using didactic strategies effectively improved students’ scientific inquiry skills.

TABLE 2
RESULTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROBLEMATIZES SITUATIONS

Level	Control group				Experimental group			
	Pretest		postest		Pretest		Pretest	
	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%
Beginner	30	96.8	20	64.5	29	93.5	0	0
Process	1	3.1	11	35.5	2	6.5	0	0
Expected Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	12.9
Outstanding Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	27	87.1
Total	31	100.0	31	100.0	31	100.0	31	100.0

Fig. 2 Results of the development of problematizes situations

In table 2 and Figure 2 shows in the pretest, both the control and experimental groups obtained similar results, remaining at the initial and in-progress levels. In the post-test, however, the experimental group reached 12.9% at the expected achievement level and 87.1% at the outstanding level, demonstrating that the program improved students' ability to problematize situations within scientific inquiry.

TABLE 3
RESULTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT, DESIGN STRATEGIES

Level	Control group				Experimental group			
	Pretest		postest		Pretest		postest	
	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%
Beginner	28	90.3	20	64.5	31	100	0	0
Process	3	9.7	11	17.7	0	0	0	0
Expected Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	22.6
Outstanding Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	77.4
Total	31	100.0	31	100.0	31	100.0	31	100.0

Fig. 3 Results of the development design strategies

In table 3 and Figure 3, it shows that, in the pretest, both the control and experimental groups obtained similar outcomes, remaining at the initial and in-progress levels. However, in the post-test, the experimental group achieved 22.6% at the expected achievement level and 77.4% at the outstanding level, demonstrating that the program enhanced students' ability to design strategies within scientific

TABLE 4
RESULTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT, GENERATE AND RECORD DATA

Level	Control group				Experimental group			
	Pretest		postest		Pretest		postest	
	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%
Beginner	29	93.5	23	74.2	30	96.8	0	0
Process	2	6.5	8	12.9	1	3.2	0	0
Expected Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	19	61.3
Outstanding Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	38.7
Total	31	100.0	31	100.0	31	100.0	31	100.0

Fig. 4 Results of the development, generate and record data

Figure 4, The pretest results showed that students from both the control and experimental groups had similar outcomes, remaining at the initial and in-progress levels. In the post-test, the experimental group achieved 61.3% at the expected achievement level and 38.7% at the outstanding level, demonstrating that the program enhanced students' ability to generate and record data within scientific inquiry.

TABLE 5
RESULTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT, DATA ANALYSIS SKILLS

Level	Control group				Experimental group			
	Pretest		postest		Pretest		postest	
	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%
Beginner	27	87.1	25	80.6	29	93.5	0	0
Process	4	12.9	6	19.4	2	6.5	1	3.2
Expected Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	25	80.6
Outstanding Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	16.1
Total	31	100.0	31	100.0	31	100.0	31	100.0

Fig.5 eResults of data analysis skills

In the pretest, both the control and experimental groups showed similar results, remaining at the beginning and developing levels. In the post-test, the experimental group demonstrated 3.2% at the developing level, 80.6% achieving the expected level, and 16.1% reaching the outstanding level. These results reveal that the program significantly improved students' data analysis skills within scientific inquiry.

TABLE 6
RESULTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT, EVALUATION AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS

Level	Control group				Experimental group			
	postest		Pretest		postest		posprueba	
	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%	fi	f%
Beginner	31	100	26	83.9	30	96.8	0	0
Process	0	0	5	8.1	1	3.2	0	0
Expected Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	29
Outstanding Achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	22	71
Total	31	100.0	31	100.0	31	100.0	31	100.0

Fig.6 Results of evaluation and communication skills

In table and Figure 6, both the control and experimental groups showed similar results in the pretest, remaining at the beginning and developing levels. In the post-test, the experimental group achieved 29% at the expected level and 71% at the outstanding level, demonstrating that the program based on didactic strategies enhanced students’ evaluation and communication skills within scientific inquiry.

TABLE 7
GROUP CONTRAST OF THE DEVELOPMENT, EVALUATION

	Indagating scientific Pre test	Indagating scientific Pos test
U de Mann_Whitney	372,500	,000
W_Wilcoxon	868,500	496,000
Z	-1,546	-6,788
Sig. asin(bil)	,122	,000

a. Variable_agrupación: Grupos

The results showed that the comparison of the scientific inquiry variable between the pre- and post-tests of the control and experimental groups yielded a p-value of 0.000; the results indicated significant differences, suggesting that the teaching strategies improved scientific inquiry. Furthermore, the post-test of the experimental group yielded a z-value of -6.788. This critical value is greater than -1.96, therefore the null hypothesis (H0) should be rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) accepted.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results obtained are consistent with those of Soplá et al. (2024), who demonstrated that applying the scientific method not only has a positive impact on the development of experimental skills for knowledge acquisition but also contributes to students’ professional growth. Similarly, Vargas Castillo (2023) found a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.724$; $p < 0.01$) between critical thinking and academic performance in Science and Technology. Although this study did not directly address scientific inquiry, it supports the use

of active strategies to strengthen scientific skills, thus providing complementary evidence for the approach adopted in the present research.

Similarly, the findings align with those of Quesada-Soto et al. (2024). During their study, four key topics were addressed, and teachers evaluated the educational platform positively, highlighting its format, content, and design. The results showed that 20% (9 students) of the control group achieved an advanced performance level, while 44% of the experimental group that used the program reached this advanced level. These outcomes indicate that students who utilized the platform demonstrated higher academic performance, suggesting that its implementation facilitated more substantial progress in learning the evaluated content. The results obtained show

In the same vein, didactic strategies represent both art and technique aimed at teaching effectively, emphasizing the importance of methodologies that facilitate learning (Herrera et al., 2023). Similarly, Colorado and Gutiérrez (2016) stated that didactic strategies consist of planned tasks designed to achieve the teaching–learning process. These strategies allow teachers to develop activities intended to foster science learning. Accordingly, scientific inquiry draws upon theoretical models such as Andrews' (1971) resource-based view, which suggests that didactic strategies enhance information comprehension, develop skills, and help identify strengths, opportunities, and challenges in order to create dynamic approaches that benefit students.

Similarly, other strategies such as collaborative learning are established, which involve leveraging students' social and emotional resources to develop teamwork skills, leadership, and conflict resolution abilities. Therefore, when this strategy is implemented in the classroom, organizing students into groups becomes essential, as it enables them to reflect and understand through collaboration and scientific communication skills (Johnson & Johnson, 1999).

The findings are supported by the theories of Novak (1977), who proposed that this approach views knowledge as a socially constructed process in which students build their own learning by drawing on their prior knowledge. Likewise, Bruner (1960) emphasized that the constructivist learning model is grounded in discovery. Both theories focus on the idea that students acquire knowledge actively through exploration and the process of discovering their own understanding.

V. CONCLUSIONS

According to the general objective, the application of didactic strategies has significant effects on the achievement of the scientific inquiry competence in the area of Science and Technology in the students of the VI cycle of secondary education of a public Educational Institution, Paracas-2024; supported with a $p = 0.000$ and $z = -6.788$ which stated that the strategies implemented developed the processes of scientific inquiry.

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